

Noncovalent Functionalization of Black Phosphorus: Free Energy Simulations vs Adsorption Experiments

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ABSTRACT: We investigate the adsorption behavior of various molecules on black phosphorus (BP), employing molecular dynamics (MD)-based free energy calculations in combination with experimental measurements. We find a semiquantitative agreement between experiment and theory. Our approach works best at the low concentration limit, as this allows us to neglect adsorbate–adsorbate interactions, both in solution and on the surface. We also conducted simulations at high concentrations to qualitatively estimate these effects and propose a suitable isotherm model for adsorbates. Our results highlight the impact of molecular structure, shape, polarity, and the alignment of adsorbates relative to the BP surface along with the solvent environment on adsorption. Our approach uses generally available methods and can be extended to arbitrary organic molecules and solvents, potentially allowing for a high throughput screening of candidate molecules for noncovalent functionalization of BP.

INTRODUCTION

Improving exfoliation and surface protection of black phosphorus while maintaining its stability and properties is a crucial precondition for its wide application in electronics and optoelectronics.^{1,2} Black phosphorus has very appealing properties such as thickness-dependent, direct band gap ranging from ~ 0.3 eV in the bulk to ~ 2 eV in the monolayer (i.e., phosphorene),^{3–7} room temperature carrier mobilities up to ~ 200 – 1000 $\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$,^{8–11} and current on/off ratios of $\sim 10^4$ – 10^5 .^{5,9} These favorable electronic properties make BP a desirable candidate for high-performance electronic and optoelectronic device applications. However, exposure of BP flakes to ambient in the long term (days) has shown etching processes and degradation, and single- and few-layer BP may deteriorate within hours.^{12,13} Simply put, the high oxophilicity of phosphorus leads to the gradual oxidation of the BP surface.¹²

Noncovalent functionalization is a promising strategy for both protecting the surface of BP and enhancing exfoliation efficiency for various applications: The Gibbs isotherm provides an exact relation between the surface tension increment of the BP–solvent interface and the surface excess of the adsorbate and its chemical activity. The surface excess in

turn can be directly computed from the potential of mean force,^{14,15} i.e., our umbrella profile. Roughly speaking, a stronger adsorption decreases the surface tension of the solvent–BP interface in proportion to its concentration. A decreased surface tension of this interface will stabilize it with respect to the multilayered crystal and thus provides a way to thermodynamically favor phosphorene formation. Hence, choosing a suitable solvent and functionalizing agents not only facilitates BP exfoliation but also ensures stable dispersion and prevents flake aggregation or precipitate, on top of protecting flakes against oxidation.^{16,17} Additionally, in noncovalent functionalization, the functionalizing molecules or solvents can be removed easily after the exfoliation process due to generally weak bonds, minimizing introducing impurities.^{16,17} Numerous solvents, including dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO),¹⁸ dimethylformamide (DMF),¹⁸ *N*-methyl-2-pyrro-

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lidone (NMP),^{19,20} *N*-cyclohexyl-2-pyrrolidone (CHP),²¹ and acetonitrile (ACN),¹⁷ have been used to exfoliate BP. In this context, the role of adsorbing cosolvents and their potential for selective adhesion to BP is a source of unexplored potential.²²

Among the known adsorbates, electrophilic molecules have attracted significant attention due to their ability to protect the surface and modulate electronic properties.^{23–32} Density functional theory (DFT) calculations in a vacuum always yield high adsorption energies; this hides the fact that in experiment many organic molecules are too well solvated to significantly adsorb to BP. Hence, we search for a simple means to predict adsorption of any molecule to BP in any given solvent.

In this study, we used an *in silico* approach: molecular dynamics simulations are a powerful tool to directly simulate adsorption isotherms using free energy methods. These isotherms in principle quantitatively illuminate adsorption phenomena. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of our methodology, we validate our simulation outcomes with experimental data.

COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

All MD simulations were performed using the GROMACS (version 2020.3) package.³³ The simulation boxes contained a $12 \times 10 \times 6$ supercell of BP (2880 atoms), the adsorbates, and solvents (acetonitrile; ACN and ethanol; EtOH). Organic molecules studied were anthracene (ANT), anthraquinone (AQ), benzyl viologen dichloride (BV), 10,10-dimethyl-9,9-biacridinium dinitrate (lucigenin), methylene blue chloride (MB), methyl viologen dichloride (MV), tetracyanoquinodimethane (TCNQ), and tetradecylpyridinium chloride (TDP). For charged adsorbates, the chloride anion was used to neutralize the system except for lucigenin, which neutralized with nitrate. Simulations were performed for MB and AQ in EtOH.

To construct the force field for BP, we chose force field parameters from Blankschtein et al.¹⁶ Adsorbates were first optimized at the MP2/6-211+G* level of theory using Gaussian 16 in the gas phase.³⁴ Single-point calculations were performed at the same level of theory to compute partial charges. The Merz–Singh–Kollman (MK)^{35,36} scheme used to calculate partial charges based on the restrained electrostatic potential (RESP).³⁷ For lucigenin and BV²⁺ we applied the same procedure at the MP2/6-211G* level of theory.

We used the General AMBER force field (GAFF)³⁸ parameters for all adsorbates. To extract force field parameters and generate topology and coordinate files for MD simulations of organic molecules, Antechamber and ACPYPE utility were employed.^{39,40} Organic molecules inserted in the box of BP and solvated with 2019 molecules of ACN (Figure 1) and

Figure 1. Side-view snapshot of a black phosphorus flake (P, orange) solvated by acetonitrile (C, black; N, blue; H, white). The simulation box contains a $12 \times 10 \times 6$ supercell of BP (2880 atoms) and 2019 molecules of ACN.

2000 molecules of EtOH. We used the AMBER force field for acetonitrile, which is an updated version of a previous AMBER force field for ACN.^{41,42} For EtOH, we used the GAFF-ESP parameters of the work by van der Spoel et al.⁴³

We also carried out DFT calculations to determine adsorption energies of experimental adsorbates in the gas phase. These calculations were performed in the gas phase using CP2K code,^{44–46} employing the Gaussian and plane waves (GPW) method.^{44–46} The core electrons of all atoms were represented by Goedecker–Teter–Hutter (GTH) pseudopotentials.⁴⁷ The geometry optimizations were performed by using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange–correlation functional,⁴⁸ with a triple- ζ valence basis set (TZVP-MOLOPT-GTH)⁴⁹ and a 400 Ry plane wave cutoff. The self-consistent field (SCF) convergence was set to 10^{-7} au, and the optimization ensured residual forces on atoms were smaller than 0.02 eV/Å. We used DFT-D3 dispersion corrections.⁵⁰ For neutral adsorbates, we employed a supercell size of $8 \times 6 \times 1$, with a vacuum space of 15 Å, similar to the approach of our previous work.³⁰ In the case of MB⁺, we calculated adsorption energy using a cluster model by Gaussian 16.³⁴ This process involved initially optimizing geometry of phosphorene and MB⁺ in a $8 \times 6 \times 1$ supercell with a vacuum space of 30 Å at the PBE/TZVP-MOLOPT-GTH level of theory. Subsequently, we saturated the optimized geometry of phosphorene with hydrogen atoms at the edges and optimized the hydrogen atoms, while keeping the MB⁺ ion and phosphorene constrained. This step was performed using CP2K at a PBE/TZVP-MOLOPT-GTH level of theory set. Finally, we performed single-point calculations on optimized structures using the polarizable continuum model (CPCM) of Tomasi and co-workers⁵¹ with Gaussian 16³⁴ at the PBE/6-21G(d,p) level of theory,⁵² applying Grimme’s D3 dispersion correction.

We performed high concentration calculations which consist of BP, solvent (2019 molecules of ACN), and 20 molecules of adsorbates while for adsorbates in EtOH we inserted 10 molecules. The systems were sampled in an isothermal–isobaric (NpT) ensemble for 1 μ s, after undergoing pre-equilibration for 2 ns. Pressure was maintained constant by Parrinello–Rahman⁵³ barostat at 1 bar using an anisotropic pressure coupling scheme and a 5.0 ps time constant. We used a CSVR⁵⁴ thermostat with a 1 ps time constant to maintain standard conditions. Long-range electrostatic interactions were treated with the particle mesh Ewald method⁵⁵ and van der Waals interactions calculated by a short-range cutoff of 1.2 nm.

Free energy profiles (ΔG) of single adsorbates were calculated using the umbrella sampling method for single adsorbates in the box of BP and ACN.⁵⁶ To generate the initial configurations of the umbrella sampling simulations, we performed a pulling simulation. For umbrella sampling, we generated 25 windows with the interval 0.2 nm between each window along the path of pulled configuration. We collected additional configurations at the region where the adsorbate laid close to the interface. The reaction coordinate defined as the distance between the center of mass of BP and the center of mass of adsorbate along the z distance. The umbrella simulations started with pre-equilibration (NpT) of 10 ns, followed by 50 ns of sampling. The starting position between BP and the adsorbate in each window was restrained with a harmonic potential and a force constant of 1500 $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-2}$. In some cases, for additional windows close to the interface, a force constant between 2000 and 3000 kJ mol^{-1}

Figure 2. (a) Comparison of gas-phase adsorption energies for neutral adsorbates and reaction-field approach for MB⁺: ΔU_{DFT} vs ΔU_{FF} . (b–d) Free energy profiles for BP + adsorbates: (b) ANT, AQ, TCNQ, MB in ACN, (c) MV, TDP, lucigenin, BV in ACN, and (d) ANT and MB in ACN, as well as AQ and MB in EtOH. The free energy profiles for (d) contains experimental samples. Adsorbates and solvents are indicated in the legend of each plot. Each plot (b–d) represents the profile as a function of the distance (z) between the center of mass of BP and the adsorbate, with a reference point of zero. Error bars across figures are standard errors obtained from bootstrapping of complete histograms.⁵⁷

nm⁻² was used. We used the same simulation conditions to maintain standard conditions. Simulations were analyzed by the weighted histogram analysis method (WHAM)⁵⁷ as implemented in the GROMACS package.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Black phosphorus was prepared by the standard method in a quartz ampule from red phosphorus using a SnI₄/Sn mineralizer. 2 g of red phosphorus was placed in a quartz ampule together with 30 mg of Sn and 60 mg of SnI₄ and melt sealed under high vacuum. Black phosphorus growth was performed in a muffle furnace by heating the ampule at 650 °C over a period of 8 h, and after 6 h the ampule was first cooled to 400 °C in 50 h, subsequently to 200 °C in 25 h, and finally freely cooled to room temperature. The ampule with black phosphorus was opened in an argon-filled glovebox. Black phosphorus was electrochemically exfoliated in the argon-filled glovebox using tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate in dimethyl sulfoxide.⁵⁸ Exfoliated black phosphorus was separated by centrifugation and transferred in acetonitrile/isopropanol (1:1 volume), and the suspension was stored in the argon-filled glovebox before further use. It was characterized with HRTEM with EDX elemental mapping (Figures S3 and S4), Raman (Figure S5) spectroscopy, XPS

(Figures S6 and S7,) and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (Figure S8). The dispersion of such prepared black phosphorus in degassed acetonitrile or ethanol was subjected to the solution of adsorbate (MB, ANT, AQ). The mixture was then separated by centrifugation at 30065 RCF for 15 min. The supernatant was carefully collected, and the measurements of absorption spectra were performed using a PerkinElmer LAMBDA 850+ UV/vis spectrophotometer (Shelton, CT) in quartz cuvettes (10.00 mm optical path). The concentration of nonadsorbed dye was calculated from the Beer–Lambert law. The number of moles of adsorbed dye was recalculated per milligram of black phosphorus and the number of milligrams of dye per milligram of black phosphorus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We used molecular dynamics-based free energy calculations with explicit solvent to estimate the adsorption free energy of various molecules on BP. For our MD simulations, we opted for the GAFF force field due to its simplicity and broad applicability. In particular, the use of GAFF makes it easy to add new adsorbates and solvents. GAFF can also be used to provide accurate bulk and solvation properties for a wide range of solvents.^{59,60} To examine the performance of the GAFF force field for adsorption on BP, we compared the adsorption

Figure 3. Adsorption isotherms (at 294 K) for experimental data (blue points) for solution: (a) BP + MB in ACN (C in 10^{-5} mol/L), (b) BP + MB in EtOH (C in 10^{-6} mol/L), (c) BP + AQ in EtOH (C in 10^{-4} mol/L), and (d) BP + ANT in EtOH (C in 10^{-5} mol/L). For each sample the adsorption capacity (q) is plotted against the concentration of adsorbate (C). The solid red line shows the fit to the experimental data. The yellow shaded areas represent the 95% confidence intervals for the predicted adsorption capacity, indicating the uncertainty around these predictions.

energies derived using GAFF parameters with those obtained from DFT calculations as illustrated in Figure 2a. The adsorption energy of neutral adsorbates was calculated in the gas phase. Electronic polarization effects for the charged MB^+ on BP cannot be modeled by standard force fields. To take them into account, we applied the reaction-field approach for both MD simulations and DFT calculations using acetonitrile permittivity.^{61,62} The satisfactory agreement between the adsorption internal energies from GAFF (ΔU_{FF}) and from DFT (ΔU_{DFT}) in our study validates the reliability of the GAFF force field for modeling the interaction energy of the adsorption of organic molecules on BP. We, therefore, continued by exploring the adsorption Gibbs free energy of various organic molecules on BP. Our simulations were carried out in ACN and EtOH (Figure 2b–d), offering a simple, swift, and effective means to predict adsorption behavior.

To test the performance of our approach in a real-world setting, we conducted experiments to assess interfacial adsorption. When comparing experimental data to simulations, caution is advised. Notably, higher concentrations present certain challenges that require a systematic discussion. Our free energy profiles correspond to a very low concentration setting on an inert surface, as there is no interaction between adsorbate/solute molecules by construction. As the concentration increases, these interactions become more significant, leading to variations in results that are dependent on the molecular properties. This results in different adsorption isotherms. With increasing concentration, interactions between adsorbates in solution and on the surface become important.

Such interactions also contradict e.g. assumptions of the Langmuir isotherm, which assumes the existence of ideal noninteracting sites. In the limit of infinite dilution, the probability of interactions between adsorbates vanishes, eliminating uncertainty about which adsorption model is suited the best. This is why we decided to focus on experimental data and MD data at low concentrations. To quantify adsorption on BP at low concentrations, we expanded the experimental adsorption capacity q (i.e., the amount of solute adsorbed per unit weight of the adsorbent) around the concentration of zero to the highest order where a statistically significant deviation from zero was observed. By statistical significance in this context, we mean that zero lies out of the 95% confidence interval (CI) on the respective coefficient. The Taylor–Maclaurin expansion up to second order (including remainder term) is for example

$$q = \left. \frac{dq}{dC} \right|_{C=0} C + \left. \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2q}{dC^2} \right|_{C=0} C^2 + O(C^3) \quad (1)$$

We define constants $a := \left. \frac{dq}{dC} \right|_{C=0}$ and $b := \left. \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2q}{dC^2} \right|_{C=0}$ which represent the first and second derivatives of q with respect to concentration C at $C = 0$. Here, C is the concentration of the adsorbate in solution. The remainder is of order $O(C^3)$ in the common big O notation.

We obtained CIs for two coefficients, a and b , by fitting the experimental data to the second-order expansion (1), and

Figure 4. (a) Plot of adsorption constants obtained from MD, a_{MD} , and experiment, a_{EXP} , on a logarithmic scale. (b) ΔG for all systems in acetonitrile (filled bars) and ethanol (empty bars).

using *t*-statistics. The results are presented in Table S1. For ANT in ACN in this table, we also reported CIs for coefficient *a* fitted only to the linear term. The fitted equation (solid line) along with the CIs for predicted adsorption capacities (yellow area) is depicted in Figure 3. Given that the MD data represent conditions of quasi-infinite dilution, our analysis primarily considers the linear term, which is reflective of ideal adsorption behavior, i.e., behavior near $C = 0$. From Table S1, we see that for all samples the estimate for coefficient *a* does not contain zero in its confidential interval, indicating significant contribution of linear term to the model's fit at the 95% confidence level.

We apply the fundamental assumption of ideal adsorption, a model that simplifies the adsorption process by treating the adsorbent surface as a featureless, uniform plane. This implies that the concept of discrete adsorption sites is essentially nonexistent in this model, making no distinction between different parts of the surface. We assume, near infinite dilution, the interactions between solute molecules in solution are negligible. Also, the presence of one adsorbate molecule on the surface has no effect on the adsorption of another molecule, an assumption critical at extremely low concentrations. Additionally, the model assumes uniform surface energy across the adsorbent, meaning that the adsorption energy remains constant, and every part of the surface has an equal potential to adsorb a molecule. To compare the experimental adsorption constant (a_{exp}) with MD data (a_{MD}), we used the linear term of eq 1. From statistical mechanics, the concentration near the surface is⁶³

$$C(\mathbf{r}) = C_{\text{bulk}} e^{-\beta F(\mathbf{r})} \quad (2)$$

where $F(\vec{r})$ is the (relative) free energy for a solute at position \vec{r} , which is set to zero in the bulk solution, and $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$. By integrating the solute concentration over interfacial layer *I* and dividing by the surface area (*S*), we obtain the surface density (*n*) of adsorbed molecules in mol/nm²:

$$n = \frac{C_{\text{bulk}}}{S} \int_I e^{-\beta F(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r} \quad (3)$$

Using the molar mass of adsorbate (M_{ads}) and the mass of adsorbent (M_S), we obtain the adsorption capacity (*q*) “the mass of adsorbed material per mass of adsorbent” as

$$q = \frac{M_{\text{ads}} C_{\text{bulk}}}{M_S} \int_I e^{-\beta F(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

From eq 1, where $q = a C_{\text{bulk}}$ we derive the theoretical adsorption constant, a_{MD} :

$$a_{MD} = \frac{M_{\text{ads}}}{M_S} \int_I e^{-\beta F(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r} \quad (5)$$

Expressing M_S as a function of BP's density (ρ) and its thickness (*t*), a_{MD} is modified:

$$a_{MD} = \frac{M_{\text{ads}}}{S \rho t} \int_I e^{-\beta F(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r} \quad (6)$$

In our model, the thickness of BP is an unknown parameter that influences a_{MD} ; it is of course also an interesting experimental observable. We, therefore, introduced an offset parameter, γ , into the equation of a_{MD} to adjust our theoretical adsorption constant. Solving eqs 1 and 2 in the Supporting Information, we found γ to be -0.13 . We plotted $\log a_{MD}$ versus $\log a_{exp}$ incorporating this scaling factor in a_{MD} (eq 3 in the Supporting Information).

Figure 4a illustrates the qualitative agreement of our MD results with experimental findings. In the next step, we estimated the Gibbs free energy change at low concentrations for various adsorbates, which are potentially difficult to measure experimentally due to their redox activity.³⁰ Using the integral from eq 5 and dividing by the interfacial layer thickness (L_0), we obtained ΔG using the following equation:

$$\Delta G = -k_B T \log \left(\frac{\int_I e^{-\beta F(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r}}{L_0 S} \right) \quad (7)$$

The L_0 was chosen to coincide with the bulk behavior of the adsorbate, and its value is 2 nm for all adsorbates, except for BV which is 2.5 nm. Figure 4b displays the Gibbs free energy profiles at low concentrations for these adsorbates.

Our PMF results indicate that MB^+ has strong affinity to the BP surface, which is also supported by the experimental adsorption constant. To understand why MB^+ adsorbs more strongly than other adsorbates, we calculated Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential values for interactions between P and S at a distance of 0.33 nm and between P and C at a distance of 0.32 nm molecule, as these are representative distances in the simulation. Using nonbonded parameters obtained from the GAFF force field, we calculated the LJ potential following Lorentz–Berthelot combination rules.^{64,65} The calculated LJ potential for the P–S interaction is notably higher (2.86 kJ/mol) than that for the P–C interaction (1.70 kJ/mol), indicating that stronger interaction of phosphorus with sulfur than with carbon. This suggests that the sulfur atom in MB^+ contributes significantly to its adsorption energy, leading to a stronger adsorption compared to other aromatic compounds lacking this feature. Our PMF results along with experimental measurements also highlight the effect of solvent on the adsorption of MB^+ . Based on our results, MB^+ shows stronger binding to BP in ACN compared to EtOH. This observation suggests that MB^+ is more soluble in EtOH, or it interacts more favorably with EtOH. This outcome is surprising, considering the higher permittivity of ACN relative to EtOH. We initially anticipated the reverse adsorption trend, where the increased solubility of MB^+ in ACN, owing to its higher dielectric constant, would lead to reduced adsorption on BP with respect to MB^+ in EtOH. Consequently, the higher adsorption observed in ACN suggests that factors other than solvent permittivity might be at play. While these factors were not directly investigated in our study, we have proposed some possible explanations. Although ACN's higher dielectric constant typically enhances solubility of ionic species, specific interactions such as hydrogen bonding or dipole interactions in EtOH might engage more strongly with MB^+ . This could result in higher solubility of MB^+ in EtOH and reducing its tendency to adsorb on BP. This difference can make it energetically unfavorable for MB^+ in EtOH to leave the solvent and adsorb on the surface. Notably this experimentally observable difference is correctly reproduced by our MD approach.

We have also conducted simulations at high concentrations for all molecules under study. At high concentrations, assumptions of ideal adsorption do not apply as the adsorbate–adsorbate interactions in solution and on the surface are not negligible. Based on the finding presented in Figure 5 and the density profiles depicted in Figure S1, we have categorized these molecules as follows: those that aggregate in solution (MV^{2+} , lucigenin), those that aggregate on the surface (MB^+), those that aggregate in both solution and on the surface (BV^{2+}), and those that exhibit single adsorption sites without visibly affecting neighboring sites and a monolayer adsorption, which is characteristic of Langmuir behavior (AQ, ANT, TCNQ, and TDP⁺). For molecules that indicate that they might be well-approximated by Langmuir behavior, we have estimated Langmuir adsorption constants in the Supporting Information (Table S2 and Figure S2). Our simulations at high concentrations also indicate that MB molecules stack on the surface. Consequently, a Langmuir fit to MB adsorption is probably not a reliable marker for measuring surface area. A Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) isotherm

Figure 5. Snapshots from simulation of highly concentrated adsorbate solutions on BP (P, orange) in acetonitrile (ACN molecules omitted for clarity) after equilibration. Top-down view: (a) BP + AQ, (b) BP + ANT, (c) BP + TDP, (d) BP + TCNQ, (e) BP + MB (left, top-down view; right, side view). Side view: (f) BP + BV and (g) BP + MV. Color: C, black; N, blue; O, red; S, yellow; H, white; Cl, green.

might be more appropriate. In our high-concentration adsorption simulations on BP, we observed distinct behaviors among various adsorbates. The charged, flat MB molecule, with its extensive π -electron system, showed the strongest adsorption on BP, a fact that was already visible in the QM calculations. This stronger adsorption may be enhanced by the S atom in MB^+ structure, enhancing dispersion interaction with BP. The formation of stacking layers of MB^+ on the BP surface, in contrast to other flat geometries with π -electron systems, indicates that factors such as molecular alignment on BP might be important. Our high concentration simulations show that the planar and neutral adsorbates like AQ, ANT, and TCNQ

form single-layer adsorption on the BP surface. Although these molecules have π systems, they are dipole-free adsorbates. On the other hand, dicationic π -conjugated molecules, which have the dipole moment, show slight adsorption (BV^{2+}) and negligible adsorption (MV^{2+} and lucigenin). This might be due to the enhanced electrostatic repulsion between the positively charged molecules or because molecules become more solvated and stabilized by the solvent. In particular, the partial desolvation of a molecule near the low-permittivity BP surface can be expected to be very costly for dications. This indicates the increase of charge has a negative effect on the adsorption.

We noted that experimental procedures involving MB^+ were relatively straightforward compared to those neutral flat adsorbates with π systems like AQ and TCNQ. Although these latter adsorbates did show adsorption on BP in our simulations, measuring them experimentally was challenging, most likely due to their redox activity on BP.³⁰ Despite the fact that TCNQ (sublimate) was proven to protect mechanically exfoliated black phosphorus,⁶⁶ in our measurements we faced difficulties. We could not determine the quantity of adsorbate due to complex changes in absorption spectra upon contact of TCNQ with BP. The BP used in this study contains oxide species. The BP used in this study contains oxide species. The XPS spectra, the P 2p core-level peaks shown in Figures S6 and S7, indicate that the surface of BP is partially oxidized. Also, the vibrations of the P_xO_y groups⁶⁷ can be found in ATR-FTIR spectrum (Figure S8), with broad-band maxima positioned at 985, 1079, and 1201 cm^{-1} .⁶⁸ However, as shown in the Raman spectrum (Figure S5), the SAED pattern and HRTEM (Figure S3) images prove the uniformity of BP structure of the flake and thin film. The A_g^1 band occurs at 357 cm^{-1} , while the B_{2g} and A_g^2 bands are located at 432 and 462 cm^{-1} , respectively. These Raman shifts are in line with the literature data.⁵⁸ Moreover, in the HRTEM images an interplanar distance of 0.44 nm has been found, which corresponds to the interplanar spacing of the (002) plane in orthorhombic crystalline black phosphorus,⁶⁹ evidenced by a clean SAED pattern (Figure S3d). We believe the effect of partial oxidation of BP does not significantly impact its qualities.

Our simulations indicate that the adsorption efficiency of molecules on the BP surface is influenced by their alignment with the surface. Despite the structural similarities between BV^{2+} and MV^{2+} , including two positively charged bipyridinium cores, BV^{2+} shows slight adsorption, whereas MV^{2+} does not adsorb. This difference could be attributed to the benzyl group in BV^{2+} interacting with the BP surface. In contrast, the lack of adsorption by MV^{2+} might be because they cannot achieve an orientation that leads to adsorption, potentially due to the presence of their methyl groups and the positive charge on each of the pyridinium rings. Another example of the effect of molecular shape and orientation is seen in dicationic lucigenin, which does not adsorb on the BP surface. The presence of charges as well as nonflat geometry of lucigenin influences its ability to align effectively on the BP surface, resulting in no adsorption.

Our simulations further indicated that effective adsorption is not confined to π -electron systems. Molecules with long aliphatic chains, which are inherently hydrophobic, such as TDP^+ , also showed an affinity for adsorption on the BP surface. This observation aligns with experimental evidence regarding the stabilization and exfoliation capabilities of ionic surfactants.^{70,71}

Overall, the efficacy of adsorption on BP surface is governed by various factors. Our study shows that merely having π -conjugated systems does not guarantee successful adsorption on BP. Instead, adsorption behavior is influenced by a combination of molecular properties including structure, shape, and polarity as well as the molecule's alignment relative to the BP surface. Additionally, the surrounding solvent environment plays a pivotal role in modulating these interactions. Based on our findings, we propose that heterocyclic compounds featuring S atoms—such as phenothiazine and thiophene—could serve as promising candidates for adsorption onto BP surfaces. We also propose that sulfur-containing surfactants with long aliphatic chains could improve adsorption on the BP surface. Given BP's susceptibility to environmental oxidation, assessing the stability of these surfactant–BP systems under experimental conditions is crucial.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, our *in silico* study employing molecular dynamics simulations has successfully estimated the relative adsorption behavior of various molecules on black phosphorus. Utilizing the Generalized Amber Force Field for molecular dynamics simulations and validating it against density functional theory calculations and experimental adsorption isotherms, we provide a semiquantitative assessment of adsorption energies and behaviors. We find a qualitative agreement between MD simulations and experimental data, at low concentrations, where ideal adsorption conditions can be assumed.

We have also conducted simulations at high concentrations for all the molecules under investigation. Our results caution against uncritically fitting model isotherms to adsorption data. Methylene blue in particular is not expected to exhibit Langmuir-type adsorption.

Due to the difficulty of obtaining clean BP, and the ambiguity of experimental results, molecular dynamics simulations are an attractive way to prescreen adsorption behavior. Our results provide principles for the effective design of adsorption on black phosphorus and the enhancement of the LPE process, derived from our MD simulations and experimental measurements: Heuristically, we suggest prioritizing flat heterocyclic compounds with sulfur atoms. However, effective adsorption is not restricted to flat molecules with π -electron systems. Molecules with nonplanar structure and hydrophobic alkyl chains can also enhance adsorption.

Finally, solvation is critical to adsorption behavior. Factors such as solvent polarity and its capacity to stabilize and dissolve the adsorbates are crucial. These effects can be unpredictable but are captured well by MD simulations. On a more skeptical note, MD simulations deliver an ideal-world adsorption picture, which may be complicated by redox effects and interactions not within the scope considered by the model.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.4c02403>.

Table of confidence intervals for coefficients a and b , calculation of offset parameter, density profiles of high concentration, high concentration calculations, TEM and HRTEM images of the BP flake, SAED pattern of the flake, TEM EDX elemental mapping of the BP flake,

Raman spectrum of BP flake, XPS spectra of the electrochemically exfoliated BP, XPS survey spectrum of the BP film on silicon substrate, and ATR-FTIR spectrum of the electrochemically exfoliated BP film (PDF)

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Notes

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